

FORMAÇÃO DA ATITUDE BASEADA NOS VALORES DOS ALUNOS EM RELAÇÃO À FUTURA PROFISSÃO DOCENTE COMO BASE MORAL DA ÉTICA PEDAGÓGICA

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' VALUES-BASED ATTITUDE TO THE FUTURE TEACHING PROFESSION AS MORAL BASIS OF PEDAGOGICAL ETHICS

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЦЕННОСТНОГО ОТНОШЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ К БУДУЩЕЙ ПРОФЕССИИ УЧИТЕЛЯ КАК МОРАЛЬНОЙ ОСНОВЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ЭТИКИ

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RESUMO

O artigo é dedicado ao estudo do problema da formação da atitude baseada em valores dos estudantes modernos em relação à futura profissão. A ética pedagógica é a base teórica, metodológica e moral da formação dos valores humanísticos dos futuros professores que são considerados diretrizes "eternas" na formação profissional e na atividade pedagógica. A urgência do problema é justificada pelos requisitos modernos de educação profissional que visam melhorar as qualidades individuais de uma pessoa para formar seu pensamento inovador e autoconsciência moral. O objetivo do estudo foi considerar a praticabilidade de incluir a disciplina "Ética Pedagógica" no currículo do programa de treinamento "Educação Pedagógica" como um dos componentes importantes que criam uma base moral para dominar o sistema de valores profissionais humanísticos e entrar na comunidade profissional. As características do desenvolvimento da orientação humanística da personalidade dos alunos e a estrutura de sua esfera de valores são descritas e as conexões entre vários tipos de valores, orientação geral, componente criativo e auto-estima são reveladas. Os métodos de humanização da formação da personalidade dos jovens estudantes são propostos no quadro do sistema educacional moderno e das realidades sociais. Os resultados diagnósticos dos estudantes modernos apresentados no artigo permitem propor uma série de tarefas inovadoras de treinamento e educação profissional na universidade. Em particular, a formação de competências profissionais entre os alunos está associada à necessidade de dominar os valores humanísticos tradicionais, que muitas vezes não coincidem com as características pessoais modernas dos futuros professores. O desenvolvimento de valores, o conhecimento do mundo e a formação da própria imagem com base na cultura da sociedade estão se tornando componentes importantes da educação moderna e da auto-educação profissional.

Palavras-chave: filosofia da educação, ética pedagógica, valores da educação profissional, orientações baseadas em valores.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the problem of the formation of the values-based attitude of modern students to the future profession. Pedagogical ethics is the theoretical, methodological, and moral basis for the creation of prospective teachers' humanistic values, which are considered "eternal" guidelines in vocational

training and pedagogical activity. The urgency of the problem is justified by the modern requirements for professional education, which is aimed to improve a person's individual qualities to form his innovative thinking and moral self-awareness. The purpose of the study was to consider the practicability of including the discipline "Pedagogical Ethics" in the curriculum of the training program "Pedagogical Education" as one of the essential components that create a moral basis for mastering the system of humanistic professional values and entering the professional community. The features of the development of the humanistic orientation of students' personality and the structure of their value sphere are described and the connections between various types of values, general orientation, creative component and self-esteem are revealed. The methods of humanization of the formation of young students' personalities are proposed in the framework of the modern education system and social realities. The diagnostic results of advanced students presented in the paper make it possible to put forward a number of innovative tasks of vocational training and education at the university. In particular, the formation of professional competencies among students is associated with the need to master traditional humanistic values, which often do not coincide with the modern personal characteristics of future teachers. The development of values, the knowledge of the world and the formation of one's image based on the culture of the society are becoming essential components of modern education and professional self-education.

Keywords: *philosophy of education, pedagogical ethics, values of professional education, values-based orientations.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена исследованию проблемы формирования ценностного отношения к будущей профессии у современных студентов. Педагогическая этика является теоретической, методологической и моральной основой формирования гуманистических ценностей будущих учителей, которые считаются «вечными» ориентирами в профессиональной подготовке и педагогической деятельности. Актуальность проблемы обоснована современными требованиями к профессиональному образованию, которое направлено на повышение индивидуальных качеств человека, формирование его инновационного мышления и нравственного самосознания. Цель исследования - рассмотреть возможность включения дисциплины «Педагогическая этика» в учебный план направления подготовки "Педагогическое образование" как одного из важных компонентов, создающих нравственную основу освоения системы гуманистических профессиональных ценностей, вхождения в профессиональное сообщество. Авторы раскрывают особенности развития гуманистической направленности личности студентов и структуру их ценностной сферы. Выявлены связи между различными видами ценностей, общей направленностью, творческой составляющей и самооценкой. Предлагаются способы гуманизации формирования личности студенческой молодёжи в рамках современной системы образования и социальных реалий. Представленные в статье результаты диагностики современных студентов позволяют выдвинуть ряд инновационных задач профессионального обучения и воспитания в вузе. В частности, формирование у студентов профессиональных компетенций связано с необходимостью освоения традиционных гуманистических ценностей, что зачастую не совпадает с современными личностными свойствами будущих педагогов. Освоение ценностей, познание окружающего мира и формирование собственного образа на основе культуры общества становятся важными компонентами современного образования и профессионального самообразования.

Ключевые слова: *философия образования, педагогическая этика, ценности профессионального образования, ценностные ориентации*

1. INTRODUCTION:

New conditions for the formation of future teachers are characterized by a high intensity of sociocultural processes, which, of course, leads to a change in the values of society, affects both the development of pedagogical science as a whole and the content of teacher education. Meanwhile, the basis for the development of any profession is the adoption of precisely those moral standards that determine the attitude to professional activity, a person's place in it, understanding and fulfillment of professional duty based on spiritual and moral self-improvement. That is why, as never before,

the most important goal of modern university education is self-education, moral self-education, and self-development of the personality of the future teacher. Consequently, the preparation of a future teacher for professional activities at a university should be aimed not only at improving the quality of education, when knowledge, skills become absolute value, and, first of all, at enhancing an individual's personal qualities, the formation of his innovative thinking, and moral self-awareness of future teachers (Pasternak, 2008).

Modern researchers conclude that the urgent problem of university education is the creation of conditions for solving the issues of

ethical training of future professionals (Greibenkina *et al.*, 2016). This study aimed to formulate concerning the modern requirements for preparing a future teacher, consider the conditions and features of including "Pedagogical Ethics" in the curriculum as one of the essential disciplines that create the basis for mastering the system of professionalism values and entering the professional community.

The concept "value" was introduced into scientific terminology by the German philosopher I. Kant in the eighteenth century. In his work "Critique of Practical Reason" (1788), he considers value as a goal, as a meaning, as an ideal to strive for: "The knowledge of value, their mental perception and experience are based on fundamental feelings, primarily such as feelings of Love, and striving for Good, Truth and Beauty." He formulated the universal moral principle of humanistic education (the principle of freedom) and defined the humanity of relations as a sense of good and communication between a teacher and a student in the educational process (Kant, 1965).

The Austrian philosopher, psychologist W. Frankl (XX century) argued that values act as conceptual universals, playing the role of the meanings of human life. These include values of creativity, values of experience, values of attitude (New values of education, 1995: 109, 110). American psychologist A. Maslow (XX century), the founder of humanistic psychology, created a system of values and needs. Human uniqueness he considered to be the principal value of an individual's personality (New values of education, 1995).

Representatives of sociological science were also actively involved in the development of value problems, having made the most critical conclusion about social values. They believed that social values being interpreted through the prism of individual life activity, become personal values and a source of motivation for behavior. So, M. Weber thought that values are not only the motive of a human act but also are the fundamental norms of all types of actions. Values form beliefs expressed in specific commandments or requirements, according to which a person creates his life, follows his duty (Kravchenko, 2001). Of course, this conclusion is important for the study of the features of vocational education.

In the '80s of the twentieth century, pedagogical axiology began to develop as an independent branch in the national philosophy of education, as a philosophical doctrine of values.

Russian philosophers, teachers, and psychologists (L.A. Belyaeva, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, A.I. Kochetov, N.B. Krylova, V.A. Slastenin, G.I. Chizhikova, and others) comprehensively considered the idea of value and its development, value priorities for the modernization of Russian education, justified the need and the path to the transition to a value educational paradigm. V.A. In the textbook for students of higher educational institutions, "Introduction to Pedagogical Axiology," Slastenin and G. I. Chizhikova examined the substantive and functional components of pedagogical axiology as an interdisciplinary field of psychological and pedagogical knowledge. They show the values-based priorities of the modernization of Russian education, give proof of the need and consider the ways of moving from the authoritarian to the humanistic educational paradigm (Slastenin *et al.*, 2003).

In the '90s of the XXth century and at the beginning of the XXIst, the Institute of Pedagogical Innovations of the Russian Academy of Education published the scientific series "New values of education" ("Thesaurus-95"; "Thesaurus-2005"), devoted to the problems of philosophy of education. It included many issues briefly characterizing the philosophical doctrine of values, the content of which contains the general idea of an axiological approach to modern culture.

The first issue of "The Thesaurus for Teachers and School Psychologists" provides a brief description of the key concepts of the axiology of modern education, personality-oriented pedagogy, and psychology, didactics, and design theory of innovative educational systems. It reveals new meanings of educational activities in different countries. The second issue describes the new approaches (subjective, communicative, cultural, problematic) to the analysis of the content of humanistic education based on the goals of personality-oriented pedagogy. The third and fourth issues are characterized by various concepts of modernization of modern education; new ideas of pedagogy, psychology, and philosophy of education, problems of the interaction of the environment, education and development of children and adolescents, interconnections of communities and education are noted, foreign practical experience of different countries of Europe and the USA is widely represented.

In Thesaurus 2005, tasks are formulated, and the characteristic of the new situation in the development of education is described, in particular, new ideas of values-based education,

purposes of humanization and individualization of educational processes, cultural values and cultural-like methods of education and training are described, interest in the development of the socio-cultural space of the school is noted.

Currently, many scientists in their pedagogical studies show constant interest in the problem of the formation of values-based orientations of a person, values-based attitude to the teaching profession. The need to solve this problem of higher education is indicated by many teachers and psychologists, researchers and practitioners, founders of scientific schools (V.I. Andreev, E.I. Artamonova, M.A. Galaguzova, A.I. Kochetov, N.B. Krylova and many others). In particular, their conceptual ideas of updating the higher education system, training future specialists based on universal values, are presented in modern educational concepts, education programs, and vocational training.

Integrated psychological and pedagogical knowledge on the reorientation of the interaction of subjects of training and education towards innovative professional activities, subject-subject relationships in modern society, and the development of innovative educational technologies are of particular importance. A well-known teacher, A.I. Kochetov wrote that three "pillars" will be the foundation of pedagogy of the future: self-knowledge, creativity, and self-improvement, he also emphasized that "education as creativity, self-knowledge as self-study in the process of exploring life itself" will be created" (Kochetov, 1996).

A detailed analysis of the conceptual ideas of scientists and teachers on the problem under study is presented in the theoretical part of our research.

Thus, the formation of students' values-based attitude to the future teaching profession is the basis of professional education. This study aimed to consider the features of the introduction of the discipline "Pedagogical Ethics" in the curriculum as one of the essential subjects that create a moral basis for mastering the system of professional values and entering the professional community.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In determining the methodological base of the study, the authors relied on the philosophy of education, which focuses on the study of the most significant objects such as the problems of the essence and content of education, training and

upbringing in their interconnection, as well as the issue of man as a subject of pedagogical activity. An equally crucial methodological problem under current conditions is the refinement and concretization of the conceptual apparatus for further developing of pedagogical theory, updating the content and improving the quality of professional education.

The subject of this research is the formation of professional values of the future teacher in the system of pedagogical ethics (moral standards of human behavior, individual's attitude to his profession). When organizing a holistic pedagogical process at a university (training and education of bachelors) to form values-based orientations and treat the pedagogical job as values, the authors relied on a combination of the following methodological approaches: axiological, humanistic, cultural, competent, communicative, personality-oriented, systemic active, professionally-oriented, creative, technological, integrative. All of them are interconnected and, altogether, provide a professionally oriented, cultural-like, moral, and communicative-integrative orientation of the process of forming value-based adjustments. Consider the substantive aspects of these approaches.

The importance of the axiological (value) approach is very significant as it provides support for the philosophical doctrine of the nature of benefits, their place in reality and the structure of the value world, i.e., about the relationship of various values among themselves, their dependence on social and cultural factors and an individual's structure. The axiological approach in the study includes orienting the teacher to universal, national and professional values, a values-based orientation in pedagogical activity. Considering education as a multi-aspect value, scientists distinguish its universal, state, social and personal values. When solving a scientific problem, the following principles were used as a whole: humanization, creativity, unity of theory and practice, integration, continuity (Ravkin, 1995). The conceptual apparatus presented in the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" (Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" 2012) and the updated requirements of the Federal State Standard for Higher Education of a New Generation for the Training of Future Teachers were also taken into consideration.

For example, the principle of humanization requires orientation on humanism as the worldview and moral basis for the formation and development of the personality of the teacher and

his students. Humanism, as a quality and ideological principle of personality, is the theoretical basis of the category of "humanitarian," meaning human individuality, its spirituality, upbringing, and education. Humanistic pedagogy aims to educate a free, creative person who can live and create in a democratic society. A personality-oriented approach in vocational education provides the creation of humanistic conditions aimed at developing a competent person, the organization of educational interaction between a teacher and a student when a student is considered as a universal human value and everyone is capable of self-education, self-development, self-determination, the formation of creative abilities.

No less important and relevant is the principle of cultural conformity, proclaimed by Disterweg in the XIX century, which became the basis of the culturological approach. The essence of the policy of cultural compliance lies in the fact that education meets the needs of the times, human development and the degree of culture the people are at. The culturological approach involves introducing the personality of the teacher into universal learning, the teacher's self-realization in culture and the development of his own social and professional position on this basis. In turn, the teacher's culture is a means and condition of the pedagogical activity, the foundation of educational mastery. The theory of the culturological approach, developed by V.A. Slastenin and his scientific school (XXI century), is used in the given study to determine the influence of the general and pedagogical culture on the development of teacher's professional competence when using interactive technologies in the learning process to achieve high performance. The system-activity approach in the implementation of the Federal State Educational Standard is oriented to the final result. It is a system-forming factor of activity and a component of forming the standards that consider professional education primarily as mastering professional experience.

The main methods of our research were a retrospective analysis and review of the literature on the problem, observation, questioning, interviews, interviewing, designing, modeling, monitoring, experiment, generalization of the experience of pedagogical activity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In the theoretical part of the research, the essence of the problem of studying the values of modern professional education and pedagogical

ethics as the moral basis for the formation of future teachers' values-based attitude to their pedagogical activity and profession was studied in detail.

As it was written above, the category "value" has a semantic closeness with the category "values-based orientations." It is a multi-valued concept, reflecting everything that is realized and experienced by a person as actual significance, as meaning, as an ideal, as the essential characteristics of an individual's consciousness and behavior, and as target constructs of social activity. Values-based orientations appear to be a system of personality aspirations and as a character of this aspiration. They can also be considered as the highest level of ideas about ideals, about the meanings of life and activity that determine the activity of each person. In the category "values-based orientations," there is a direct indication of the existence of a life guide that defines the vector of personal development.

Value can also serve the purpose of human existence. In this regard, the authors agree with the opinion of V.A. Slastenin and E.I. Artamonova, who write about the significance of the characteristics of spiritual values. According to their viewpoint, building a hierarchy of values is associated with a personal worldview, the formation of self-awareness, and is based on the analysis of axiological structures vital for a person: ideals, beliefs, principles (Slastenin, Artamonova, 2002).

Considering pedagogical activity as a value for the development of the personality of the teacher and university students, it was necessary to review the content and methods of training and education. As a result, the future specialist will be "equipped" with knowledge and skills, moral standards, which prepare them for life and practical work. Therefore, it is vital to consider the essence of the term "ethics" (theoretical and practical philosophical science of morality) that has a rather long history: in the 4th century BC, the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle introduced it to designate a field of knowledge that studies various virtues. It is noteworthy that even then Aristotle had in mind that ethics is aimed at human activity, and it is important to examine it not to know what virtue (moral) is, but to become virtuous, that is, to adopt a specific system of values, to cultivate noble qualities. The measure of real value, according to Aristotle, is "virtue and virtuous man as he is."

Today, research on professional ethics and the formation of the attitude of future specialists to

education as a value is very relevant. Professional ethics is the specific requirement of morality associated with the characteristics of various professions. The concept of "Pedagogical Ethics" was first formulated in Russia in the 70s of the XX century by E.A. Grishin. He argued that Pedagogical Ethics is the science of the laws of development of moral requirements generated by the characteristics of pedagogical work. These requirements are manifested in the relationships between a teacher and students, teachers and students' parents, between teachers and the administration, as well as in the existing relations of the teaching staff itself. Moral requirements are determined by the personal and professional qualities of the teacher (Grishin, 1973).

According to V.I. Andreev's opinion, under modern conditions, "Pedagogical Ethics is the science of the laws of development (self-development) and self-realization of a teacher's moral culture, which manifests itself in various situations of moral choice and moral activity in the process of solving pedagogical problems. Pedagogical ethics aims to identify, justify and formulate basic ethical laws and on their basis such professional and pedagogical principles and rules that would contribute to highly moral behavior and activities of the teacher and the work of the teacher to create a comfortable environment for all participants in the educational process". V.I. Andreev considers the preparation of a teacher for profoundly human pedagogical activity in all possible situations, at all stages of education and upbringing of the younger generation to be the final goal of "Pedagogical Ethics" (Andreev, 2012).

Scientist-teacher L.L. Shevchenko, the author of the book "Practical Pedagogical Ethics" (experimental didactic study guide, a book for teachers and parents, 1997) defines pedagogical ethics as part of ethics, the subject of which is the pattern of morality in the consciousness, behavior, relationships, and activities of the teacher. It is emphasized that the main objectives of the study guide are: "study of the theoretical problems of pedagogical morality; development of moral aspects of pedagogical work; identification of the requirements for the moral character of the teacher; the study of the moral consciousness of the teacher; study of the nature of the teacher's moral relations; development of issues of moral education and self-education of a teacher. The teacher reveals the basic concepts of pedagogical ethics: pedagogical justice, professional-pedagogical duty, professional honor and conscience, dignity, pedagogical authority, and self-discipline (Shevchenko, 1997).

In the pedagogical research of scientists, there is constant interest in the problem of the formation of a value attitude to the pedagogical profession. At the turn of the 21st century and the beginning of the 21st century, international scientific and practical conferences were held, such as: "Pedagogical education for the 21st century" (Moscow, 1994), "Problems of the formation and development of teacher's values-based orientations at the turn of the 21st century" (Tula, 1997), "Teacher Education: Challenges of the 21st Century", "Teacher Education: Challenges of the 21st Century" (dedicated to the memory of Academician of the Russian Academy of Education V. Slavenin, Ryazan, 2017), where Russian scientists and practical trainers of educational institutions (B.S. Gershunsky, L.K. Grebenkina, N.A. Zhokina, I.F. Isaev, N.V. Martishina, N.D. Nikandrov, A.A. Orlov, V.A. Slavenin, I.L. Fedotenko, E.N. Shiyanov and others) discussed the problems of the importance of the formation of values-based orientations in the process of psychological and pedagogical preparation of the future professionals and their professional activities. An analysis of conference materials allows us to note the constant attention of scientists to ethical issues, as well as highlight, in our opinion, the most significant values of professional training of future teachers.

It is essential to draw attention to a collective monograph "The conceptual apparatus of pedagogy and education" annually published by the scientists of the Ural State Pedagogical University (edited by M. A. Galaguzov, E. V. Tkachenko). It is devoted to conceptual and terminological problems and summarizing research on the challenge of future formation specialists of the values of education, the values of the teaching profession and teaching activities, due to the large-scale processes of modernization of domestic education (The conceptual apparatus of pedagogy and education, 2010).

The need for such studies was due to the adoption of the Concept for the modernization of Russian education for the period until 2010 in 2002. However, after this period, it became evident that the problems of modernization have not lost their relevance; on the contrary, they are acquiring new aspects that require further research and comprehensive understanding. To participate in the discussion of these problems, scientists are invited to explore new pedagogical phenomena and concepts that reflect the various aspects of modernization of education, its substantial and technological renewal following continually changing social realities and the latest

trends in its development. As a rule, four sections are proposed in the monograph: "Pedagogy methodology," "General pedagogy," "Professional pedagogy," and "Social and special pedagogy." So, the sixth issue of this publication (2010) is wholly devoted to the study of the problem of values and values-based orientations in education. In particular, it is considered:

1) axiological approach as a new research method in pedagogy;

2) understanding of education as a value, as a person's property, as a means of one's self-realization in life; as a means of making a person's career;

3) personal orientation of education, the idea of a person as the highest objective (value) of education;

4) direction of education on the spiritual and moral values of student's development and education.

The section "Professional Pedagogy" reveals the features of the axiological approach in vocational education: orientation on humanistic values, the formation of creativity among students in the process of university education, axiological orientation; values-based attitude to the pedagogical process and all its participants. The following values are highlighted: desire for truth; social well-being of society; social justice; moral humanistic norms; knowledge acquisition; respect for talents; decency (honesty); own dignity; personality value; social activity; your health and those around you; nature conservation; moral health of the team and society; the value of other peoples and their culture; goodwill in relationships, mutual assistance, etc. (The conceptual apparatus of pedagogy and education, 2010).

Discussing the essence of values, their place, and role in people's lives, V.A. Slastenin and the representatives of his scientific school argue that the category of value applies to the human world and society. Outside of a man and without a man, the concept of value cannot exist, since it represents a particular human type of significance of objects and phenomena. Values are not primary; they are derived from the correlation of the world and a man, confirming the relevance of what a man created in the process of history (Slastenin, Shiyanov, 1996).

Universal, state, social, and personal values are considered to be a universal priority, determining the essence of modern education, including higher education (Gershunsky, 1997: 6). Pedagogical activity is a particularly important

value of contemporary Russian society, aimed primarily at educating a humanist, patriot of Russia, focused on the priority of Russian national values with due respect for the importance of other cultures (Nikandrov, 1997).

The values of pedagogical activity serve as a guide for the teacher's social and professional event aimed at achieving socially meaningful humanistic goals in teaching and educating students. Scientists distinguish groups of universal and national values of pedagogical activity that influence the development of pedagogical skills of a teacher (Table 1):

Similar classifications are found in the works of other researchers. So, Z.I. Ravkin, classifying the pedagogical values of education, singles out the following groups: socio-political, intellectual, moral, and the group of values of professional-pedagogical activity. The scientist writes that their structure includes:

- a vocation to work as a teacher-educator,
- a consciousness of personal and social responsibility for the chosen profession;
- the talent of the teacher, his search and research, innovative activity;
- high moral personal qualities of a teacher;
- communicative abilities, a style of communication with students, based on democratic and humanistic principles (the teacher is called to love those he teaches and love what he teaches);
- the professionalism of the teacher, a high level of special and general cultural training, broad professional and broad erudition, pedagogical skills that ensure its competitive qualities in the labor market;
- consistent orientation towards the development and strengthening in the integral pedagogical process of social, intellectual, moral, and aesthetic values of education (Ravkin, 1995).

These ideas are largely reflected in recent documents. Thus, the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" (2012) affirms the humanistic nature of education among the main principles of state policy and legal regulation of relations in the field of education. However, sociological studies conducted in different years in different regions of the country show that, quite often, teachers only confine themselves to talking about humanism and recognizing the rights of schoolchildren. On the other hand, about half of the teachers surveyed do not conceal the fact that they use authoritarian methods (Timonina, 2014).

In other words, this indicates a contradiction that has existed in the education system for a long time. It also manifests itself in the professional problem: the affirmation of the humanistic principle puts the school teacher in a situation of constant sharp contradictions. Experience shows that the teacher's respect for the student does not guarantee the opposite: the teacher's respect for the student forms a consumer's attitude to teachers instead.

According to the Article 48 of the Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" "teaching staff must: comply with legal, moral and ethical standards, follow the requirements of professional ethics; respect the honor and dignity of students and other participants in educational relations (Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" 2012). This requirement also can be found in the professional standard "Teacher" (Professional Standard "Teacher," 2013). Of course, these statements are specific grounds for the formation of the tasks of professional education.

The relevance of adopting the rules of professional behavior also relates to the fact that young people who choose a pedagogical profession for themselves come with their value system, which rejects the traditional ideas about social norms, as well as about the job. Each society forms its system of values, which helps a person to choose socially approved behavior in vital situations. It is worth mentioning a critical observation noted by a researcher of the youth, I.M. Ilyinsky, who argued against the traditional perception of the youth as a product of society, believing that the young generation is a social accumulator and produces community, concentrating future ideas and values in their views (Ilyinsky, 2001). That is, there is a need to bring the value system of the young generation with the value system established in professional activity.

It is worth noting that getting higher education for a young man today is one of his life goals, and is also considered by him as a condition of professional and personal self-determination, the possibility of self-development. This is also proved by the results of our study of a young student (Martishina *et al.*, 2016). For example, one can note particular dynamics in the judgments of young people about their life goals, perceptions of the future profession. So, the initial ideas about the future profession expressed by freshmen are superficial, based on their school perception of teachers. Studies show that in the judgments of young people, on the one hand, there are idealized

characteristics, and on the other, a negative perception of the future teaching profession, fear of interacting with children, rejection of the teacher's traditional norms of behavior. In many respects, such positions reflect the existing public opinion about the teaching profession. Note that the motives for choosing a pedagogical university among applicants are very diverse: only half of the applicants have a desire to be a teacher.

Often young people postpone the decision to choose the workplace they will decide after graduating from a university, while the status of a person with higher education attracts the majority of applicants. Also, boys and girls who enter the university have a high level of dependence on parents, who influence the choice of young people and materially support their studies. In this regard, first-year students demonstrate a lack of professional orientation during the period of schooling, as well as a certain infantilism, a lack of desire to be independent, to consider a future profession seriously, and to build a career. Meanwhile, career growth should be presented precisely as a process of achieving goals. In other words, at this stage of personality formation, a particular discrepancy is noted: young people talk about their dreams or goals, build an image of the future, but they do not always adequately choose the ways to achieve the desired result, they can develop their current actions as a movement towards the goal.

In this regard, in the study, the authors used the method of revealing the life values by Milton Rokich, who proposed to consider two types of benefits: "values-goals," or terminal, and "values-means," or instrumental (Lapin, 2002). According to the scientist, the former express in general terms the most important goals, ideals, and self-valuable meanings of people's lives, for example, the value of human life, family, interpersonal relationships, freedom, labor, etc. Instrumental values reflect the means approved by society for achieving goals; these are moral standards of behavior, as well as specific qualities of a person (such as independence, initiative, authority, etc.).

This approach helps to determine the mechanisms of professional and personal formation of the future expert. The conducted study made it possible to record in modern students who are mastering the program of teacher education, the characteristic dominance of personal life values over the values of professional self-realization (Ilyinsky, 2001). Young people put happy family life in the first place, and among professional values, they highlight the possibility of self-realization. The dynamics taking place in the

selection of benefits among students of 1-2 courses of bachelor's degree, students of the four-course of bachelor's degree and among graduate students is shown in Table 2.

As it is presented in Table 2, conformist, humane values, as well as communication values, are in the first place. Ethical values are in the last place for young students; in the future, their rating increases, but slightly. Modern trends in the youth environment include students' concentration on their problems, the need for self-development, personal success, and recognition. Ethical values take the last place among junior students; they have the least interest in following the norms. Self-affirmation, self-expression among the youth are much more critical.

The rating of ethical values is rising, but not significantly. Respondents note that sometimes or only "periodically," they think about compliance with moral standards, but they understand that this is important for the future profession. Thus, there is an absolute contradiction that arises among students in the process of mastering the next trade. The difficulty of adopting moral standards, reassessing values takes time. When asked what prevents people from living, observing ethical standards, students answered that this was due to a lack of education, as well as selfishness and "herd instincts."

On the one hand, it can be noted that older students, having an individual experience of interaction in professional activities, begin to realize the importance of adopting ethical standards. But on the other hand, such results confirm the need to pay special attention to the development of the values of the future profession, to create conditions for entering the professional community, which is characterized by a system of norms, rules of behavior, communication, relationships (Martishina *et al.*, 2016).

Thus, the introduction of the "Pedagogical Ethics" in the curriculum of the teacher education program is not only justified from the point of view of vocational training tasks but also becomes a very important condition for mastering pedagogical activity, providing an adequate understanding of the interaction of participants in educational relations.

This course is based on studies of modern deontology, which is based on general ethical standards and determines the normative moral position of the teacher. Note that the focus is precisely on "oughtness" (from Greek *deon* - duty), in other words, the profession dictates the observance of specific rules, sets codes of

conduct, prescribes a particular type of moral relationship between people, requires internal self-regulation of the person based on ethical ideals. Modern textbooks on pedagogical ethics affirm the traditional categories of pedagogical justice, professional duty, honor, and conscience, pedagogical authority, dignity, and self-discipline (Vekkesser *et al.*, 2017; Timonina, 2014).

Under current conditions of professional education, "Pedagogical Ethics" as a subject reflects the specificity of moral requirements for pedagogical activity. Note that this discipline includes not only the theoretical basis for the formation of pedagogical values but also involves a large number of practical tasks and independent work of students. For example, students get acquainted with the model code of the teacher (Letter of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation of 2014) and also develop options for the professional system for teachers working in various educational institutions. Such work involves a certain "dipping" in the professional community, acquaintance with pedagogical situations, analysis of the characteristics of the interaction of participants in educational relations, the development of requirements that can become the basis for choosing value orientations, professional self-education of future teachers.

The training course "Educational Ethics" formerly was worked out to learn for students at the final course. However, young people need to orient themselves in professional requirements much earlier: in the first pedagogical practice, students find themselves in situations of difficult choice of behavior in the professional community, the choice of solving problems of interaction with children and their parents. In this regard, the study of the course "Pedagogical Ethics" is placed to an earlier stage in the curricula of various training profiles in the direction of "Pedagogical Education."

It is also worth noting that the quality of the educational process as a whole is of great importance in the training of future teachers. Ethical standards should be mastered not only within the framework of academic discipline but also presented in the real relationships of the teaching staff.

The task of modern professional education is to form not only certain competencies but also a system of professional values, without which it is impossible to imagine the fulfillment of the mission of pedagogical activity. In this regard, it is necessary to talk about the saturation of the

educational process with professional values, which should ensure the formation of the personality of the future teacher under certain conditions. It should be remembered that the values of education are goals, meanings, ideal forms of pedagogical activity aimed at professionally-personal formation and development of a specialist based on universal values (Zhokina, 2015).

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The study allows us to draw some conclusions that are important for improving the training of future teachers. In the process of scientific research, the presence of a constant interest of scientists in the problem of the formation of the values-based attitude to the teaching profession was confirmed.

A retrospective analysis of the positions of scientists in the interpretation of the axiological approach as a methodological condition for studying the values of professional education shows its unique significance. The axiological approach provides support on the philosophical doctrine of the nature of values, their structure and place in reality. This allows to orient the teacher to universal, national and professional values to form a value-related attitude to professional activities.

Pedagogical ethics constitutes a theoretical and methodological moral basis for the formation of the humanistic values of future teachers. These values are the "eternal" guidelines of their professional activity. The creator and bearer of values is a professional teacher whose primary function is to discover and improve human qualities in a person through the development of values, the knowledge of the world around him and the formation of his image based on the culture of society (Bykova, 2018).

The consistent and systematic learning of ethical principles of the profession is possible due to studying the subject "Pedagogical Ethics," plays an essential role in future teachers' training.

The analysis of theoretical sources and pedagogical experience shows that at present, goal-oriented pedagogical requirements are aimed to form a competently developed creative personality of future specialists. These goal-oriented pedagogical requirements are becoming integrative in the practical activities of university teachers. The formation of students' values-based attitude to the future teaching profession faces many obstacles associated with changing sociocultural conditions. In this regard, for the

preparation of students, a full-fledged "immersion" in the professional community is necessary. The discipline "Pedagogical Ethics" becomes the basis in the development of a system of values, rules and norms. The saturation of the educational process with events, interactions peculiar to professional activities should also be a valuable addition.

The preparation of students for the future teaching profession in modern conditions is characterized by an increase in the culture-forming function of education as a universal value. The role of a teacher with a high general and professional culture, capable of mastering and improving the culture of society as a value, passing it on to young generations is changing qualitatively.

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Table 1. *Groups of universal and national values of pedagogical activity influencing the development of pedagogical skills of a teacher*

N	Value description	Examples
11.	values associated with the adoption in society, the immediate social environment	the social significance of the teacher's work, the prestige of the teacher's professional activity, recognition of relatives, friends, etc.
22.	values related to meeting the need for communication	constant work with children, children's love and affection, opportunities to communicate with interesting people, parents, colleagues, exchange of spiritual values, etc.
33.	values related to self-improvement	the possibility of developing creative abilities, culturation with spiritual culture, doing one's favorite thing, the ability to enrich one's knowledge, etc.
44.	values associated with self-expression	(the possibility of developing creative abilities, culturation with spiritual culture, doing one's favorite thing, the ability to enrich one's knowledge, etc.
55.	values associated with utilitarian-pragmatic requests	opportunities for self-affirmation, interpersonal communication, professional growth, promotion, (Slastenin, Shiyarov, 1996: 233).

Table 2. *Comparison of the importance of values for modern students*

Types of values	Students		
	1-2 courses of bachelor's degree (134 students)	4 course of bachelor's degree (101 students)	graduate students (41 students)
	Importance of values for students (rating)		
Ethical values	8	5	6
Communication values	3	2	2
Values of work	4	3	5
Individualistic values	6	8	7
Conformist values	1	1	4
Altruistic values	2	6	1
Values of Self-Affirmation	7	7	8
Other people's acceptance values	5	4	3